

Comparative Impact of Laparoscopic versus Open Ovarian Cystectomy on Future Fertility: Analysis of Serum AMH and Antral Follicle CountNazia Nigar¹, Shweta Gupta², Monika Anant³¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, AIIMS, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, AIIMS, Patna, Bihar, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, AIIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

Background: Ovarian cysts are a common gynaecological condition that may necessitate surgical intervention. Serum Anti-Müllerian Hormone (AMH) levels and Antral Follicle Count (AFC) are key indicators of ovarian reserve. The study compared the impact of laparoscopic versus open ovarian cystectomy on future fertility by evaluating changes in serum AMH levels and AFC over a 12-month period.

Methods: Sixty patients diagnosed with benign ovarian cysts were equally divided into two groups: laparoscopic cystectomy (n=30) and open cystectomy (n=30). Data on serum AMH levels and AFC were collected at baseline, 3-, 6-, and 12 months post-surgery. Statistical analysis was accomplished using SPSS.

Results: The laparoscopic group maintained higher serum AMH levels and AFC compared to the open group at all follow-up points. Significant differences were observed at 6 months (AMH: p=0.030; AFC: p=0.020) and 12 months (AMH: p=0.005; AFC: p=0.004) post-surgery. The laparoscopic group also experienced fewer surgical complications, such as infections and haemorrhages, compared to the open group.

Conclusion: Laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy has a less negative impact on ovarian reserve and future fertility compared to open ovarian cystectomy. This is evidenced by higher serum AMH levels, greater AFC, and fewer surgical complications in the laparoscopic group.

Recommendations: Laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy should be preferred over open cystectomy for women desiring future fertility.

Keywords: Ovarian Cystectomy, Laparoscopic Surgery, Open Surgery, Ovarian Reserve, Fertility.

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Introduction

Ovarian cysts are a frequent gynaecological ailment that are sacs filled with fluid that grow on or within the ovary. Many ovarian cysts are benign and go away on their own, but some are large, persistent, or have the potential to rupture or become cancerous, in which case they need to be surgically removed. The two main surgical methods used for ovarian cystectomy are open and laparoscopic methods. Because laparoscopic cystectomy is less invasive than open cystectomy, it has become more popular because of its advantages over open cystectomy, including shorter hospital stays, faster recovery times, and less postoperative pain [1]. The effect that these surgical techniques may have on future fertility and ovarian reserve, a crucial topic for women of reproductive age, is still a source of worry.

The ability of the ovary to produce eggs that can be fertilised and result in a safe and fruitful pregnancy is referred to as ovarian reserve. Antral Follicle Count (AFC) and serum Anti-Müllerian Hormone (AMH) levels are important markers of ovarian

reserve [2]. The number of pre-antral and tiny antral follicle granulosa cells that release AMH correlates with the quantity of follicles that are still present in the ovaries. AFC is a direct indicator of the pool of recruitable follicles and is measured by transvaginal ultrasound. It counts the number of tiny antral follicles.

Regarding the effect of laparoscopic and open ovarian cystectomies on ovarian reserve, prior research has produced contradictory findings. While some studies show no discernible difference between the two procedures, others imply that laparoscopic surgery may be associated with a smaller reduction in ovarian reserve than open surgery [3, 4]. For women who want to continue to be fertile after surgery, maintaining ovarian reserve is especially important.

By comparing the effects of laparoscopic versus open ovarian cystectomy on future fertility, this study will compare the effects on serum levels of AMH and AFC.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective comparative study.

Study Setting: The study took place for a duration of at AIIMS, Patna from January 2017 to December 2018.

Participants: 60 patients (30 undergoing laparoscopic cystectomy and 30 undergoing open cystectomy).

Inclusion Criteria

1. Women aged 18-40 years.
2. Diagnosed with benign ovarian cysts.
3. No prior ovarian surgery.
4. Normal baseline serum AMH and AFC levels.
5. Desire for future fertility.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Women with malignant ovarian cysts.
2. Previous ovarian or pelvic surgery.
3. Known history of infertility.
4. Endocrine disorders affecting fertility.
5. Refusal to participate or inability to follow up.

Bias: In order to reduce selection bias, participants were randomly allocated to either the laparoscopic or open cystectomy group. The group assignments were concealed from data collectors and analysts in order to minimise the risk of detection and reporting bias.

Data Collection: At baseline (pre-surgery) and follow-up intervals (three, six, and twelve months after surgery), data were gathered. AFC and serum AMH levels were the main outcome indicators.

Procedure

1. Baseline Assessment:

- Comprehensive medical history and physical examination were conducted.
- Baseline serum AMH and AFC measurements were taken.

2. Surgical Intervention:

- Participants underwent either laparoscopic or open ovarian cystectomy as per random assignment.
- Standard surgical protocols were followed for both procedures.

3. Follow-Up:

- Serum AMH and AFC were measured at 3-, 6-, and 12-months post-surgery.
- Participants were monitored for any surgical complications or adverse effects.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to study the data. The individuals' baseline characteristics were summed up via descriptive statistics. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value < 0.05.

Result

Thirty underwent open ovarian cystectomy and thirty underwent laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy among the sixty patients in the study. Table 1 provides a summary of the participants' baseline and demographic data.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Laparoscopic Group	Open Group	p-value
Age (years)	29.6 ± 5.2	30.1 ± 5.0	0.678
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.7 ± 3.1	25.2 ± 3.4	0.501
Baseline AMH (ng/mL)	4.5 ± 1.2	4.6 ± 1.1	0.763
Baseline AFC	12.3 ± 3.5	12.0 ± 3.8	0.775
Cyst Size (cm)	5.2 ± 1.8	5.5 ± 2.0	0.586

The serum AMH levels were measured at baseline, 3-, 6-, and 12 months post-surgery. The mean serum AMH levels in both groups are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Serum AMH Levels (ng/mL)

Time point	Laparoscopic Group	Open Group	p-value
Baseline	4.5 ± 1.2	4.6 ± 1.1	0.763
3 months	4.2 ± 1.1	3.8 ± 1.0	0.120
6 months	4.1 ± 1.0	3.5 ± 0.9	0.030
12 months	4.0 ± 1.0	3.3 ± 0.8	0.005

The AFC was measured at baseline, 3-, 6-, and 12 months post-surgery. The mean AFC in both groups is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Antral Follicle Count (AFC)

Time point	Laparoscopic Group	Open Group	p-value
Baseline	12.3 ± 3.5	12.0 ± 3.8	0.775
3 months	11.5 ± 3.2	10.0 ± 3.6	0.045
6 months	11.0 ± 3.1	9.2 ± 3.5	0.020
12 months	10.8 ± 3.0	8.5 ± 3.2	0.004

The changes in serum AMH and AFC over time within and between groups were analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA. The results indicated significant differences in the changes of serum AMH and AFC between the laparoscopic and open groups over the 12-month follow-up period.

The incidence of surgical complications and adverse effects was monitored in both groups. The laparoscopic group had fewer complications compared to the open group. The details are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Surgical Complications and Adverse Effects

Complication/Adverse Effect	Laparoscopic Group	Open Group	p-value
Infection	1 (3.3%)	4 (13.3%)	0.157
Haemorrhage	2 (6.7%)	5 (16.7%)	0.233
Prolonged Hospital Stay	0 (0%)	3 (10%)	0.077
Pain	3 (10%)	6 (20%)	0.277

Discussion

There were sixty participants in all, equally divided between the two surgical procedures. An equal comparison was ensured by the demographic and baseline factors, which included age, BMI, baseline AMH, and AFC, being comparable between the two groups.

Compared to the open surgery group, the laparoscopic group continuously showed higher serum AMH levels over the course of the 12-month observation period. At first, the AMH levels in both groups were comparable. Nevertheless, the laparoscopic group had considerably higher levels of AMH than the other group at 6 and 12 months following the surgery ($p=0.030$ and $p=0.005$, respectively). These results suggest that, in comparison to open cystectomy, laparoscopic cystectomy has a less detrimental effect on ovarian reserve.

Additionally, during the course of all follow-up periods, the laparoscopic group continuously demonstrated a larger AFC in comparison to the other groups. While both groups' initial AFCs were similar, there were significant differences after 3, 6, and 12 months following surgery ($p=0.045$, $p=0.020$, and $p=0.004$, respectively). This finding adds to the body of research supporting the claim that laparoscopic cystectomy preserves ovarian function better than open cystectomy.

The study also looked at side effects and surgical complications, and it found that the laparoscopic group experienced fewer issues overall. Although not all sequelae were statistically significant, there was a discernible trend in the laparoscopic group towards fewer infections, haemorrhages, longer hospital stays, and postoperative pain.

Overall, this study's results show that, in terms of preserving future fertility, laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy is superior to open ovarian cystectomy. Elevated serum AMH and AFC levels and a reduction in surgical complications corroborate this. These results lend credence to the practical

application of laparoscopic cystectomy when future fertility preservation is a concern.

In a study, the effects of suturing versus electrocoagulation as a haemostatic method on ovarian reserve and fertility during laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy were investigated. According to the study, electrocoagulation negatively impacted ovarian reserve, causing notable decreases in AMH and E2 levels as well as an increase in FSH levels at 1 and 6 months following the procedure. Sutures were administered to the group that had better results and less impact on indicators of ovarian reserve [5].

To investigate how ovarian reserve markers were affected by laparoscopic and open ovarian cystectomies, a prospective randomised experiment was carried out. In patients between the ages of 18 and 35, the study evaluated the preoperative and three-month postoperative levels of AMH, AFC, and FSH. The findings demonstrated that there was no discernible difference in the features of ovarian reserve between the two therapies, suggesting that both processes are equally effective at protecting ovarian function [6].

An analysis evaluated the long-term impact of laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy on the results of in vitro fertilisation. The long-term ovarian reserve and IVF outcomes were found to be negatively influenced by the study, which followed patients for up to five years following surgery. This was particularly evident in cases containing endometriotic cysts. Long-term research has demonstrated a significant reduction in gonadotropin-stimulated ovarian response and AMH levels, which in turn results in a decline in the incidence of pregnancy [7].

To evaluate the maintenance of ovarian reserve in CO2 laser vaporisation against standard cystectomy, a comparative study was carried out. Compared to a normal cystectomy, the study found that CO2 laser vaporisation preserved more AMH levels and antral follicle count while having less of an effect on neighbouring healthy ovarian tissue. According to these results, vaporisation with a CO2 laser may be a

more successful method of treating endometrioma while preserving ovarian function [8].

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrated that laparoscopic ovarian cystectomy had a less negative impact on future fertility compared to open ovarian cystectomy, as evidenced by higher serum AMH levels and AFC at 12 months post-surgery. The laparoscopic group also experienced fewer surgical complications and adverse effects, suggesting that it may be a preferable surgical approach for women desiring future fertility.

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